

A compact two-descriptor ellipse model predicts magnetic microparticle swarm morphology and supports control-oriented morphology regulation

1. Motivation and contribution

Clinical motivation

- The morphology of magnetic microparticle swarms is hard to predict.
- Control needs a low-dimensional model rather than many-particle simulation.

Research gap

Few approaches provide compact parametric equations linking swarm morphology to magnetic-field descriptors for control design.

Core idea

Represent the swarm footprint as an ellipse and regulate only two geometric descriptors: r_1 and r_2 .

Contributions

- Ellipse model linking footprint descriptors to field curvature, axial gradient and rotation frequency.
- Control-oriented formulation validated by simulated MIMO PID tracking and open-loop experiments.

Fig. 2: (a) Stepper-driven spherical NdFeB magnet mounted on the robotic arm; Figure generated using Chatgpt AI from the experimental setup, (b) Dominant mechanisms

2. Experiments and regimes

Experimental Setup

Fig. 3: Experimental setup

Platform facts

- 6-DoF UR10e moves the magnetic source along Z_m .
- Spherical NdFeB magnet: radius 20 mm, continuously rotated by a stepper motor.
- NdFeB microparticles: mean diameter 5 μm ; water reservoir; camera-based footprint tracking.

Morphology map and valid region

Fig. 4: Experimental swarm morphologies used to delimit the model regime.

Fig. 5: Regime map versus magnet distance z_m and rotation frequency f_m , showing $f_{off} = 6$ Hz and $Z_{off} = 23.5$ mm

3. Reduced-order ellipse model

Input-output structure

Model assumptions

- Swarm centroid coincides with the center of the rotating magnetic field.
- Swarm envelope rotates at the applied angular velocity.
- Out-of-plane deformation is neglected.

1) Reduced-order dynamic model

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{r}_1 &= -K_{b,1} S_x(z_m) (r_1 - r_{1,min})^\beta + E(r_1, r_2; z_m, \omega_m) - K_{d,1} \dot{r}_1 \\ \dot{r}_2 &= -K_{b,2} S_y(z_m) (r_2 - r_{2,min})^\beta + E(r_1, r_2; z_m, \omega_m) - K_{d,2} \dot{r}_2 \end{aligned}$$

- Confinement (magnetic): $K_{b,i} S_i(z_m) (r_i - r_{i,min})^\beta$
- Expansion (rotation-driven): $E(r_1, r_2; z_m, \omega_m)$
- Dissipation (effective relaxation): $K_{d,i} \dot{r}_i$

2) Steady-state morphology

At steady state:

$$\dot{r}_1 = \dot{r}_2 = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} r_1(z_m, \omega_m) &= \frac{C_1 \Phi(\omega_m)}{S_x(z_m, \omega_m)^{\alpha_1}} \\ r_2(z_m, \omega_m) &= \frac{C_2 \Phi(\omega_m)}{S_y(z_m, \omega_m)^{\alpha_2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Phi(\omega_m) = \exp \left[N \left(\left(\frac{|\omega_m|}{\omega_{ref}} \right)^q - 1 \right) \right]$$

Stiffness function

$$\begin{aligned} S_x(z_m, \omega_m) &= s_0 + a_{K1} \left| k_{xx}^{(B^2)}(z_m) \right|^{\gamma_1} + a_G g_z(z_m)^\rho \\ &+ a_P \left(\frac{B(z_m)}{B_{ref}} \right)^{\mu_P} \left[1 + \log \left(1 + c_P \left(\frac{|\omega_m|}{\omega_{ref}} \right)^{q_P} \right) \right] \\ S_y(z_m, \omega_m) &= s_0 + a_{K2} \left| k_{yy}^{(B^2)}(z_m) \right|^{\gamma_2} + a_G g_z(z_m)^\rho \\ &+ a_P \left(\frac{B(z_m)}{B_{ref}} \right)^{\mu_P} \left[1 + \log \left(1 + c_P \left(\frac{|\omega_m|}{\omega_{ref}} \right)^{q_P} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Physical interpretation

Fig. 6: Collapsed frequency response supports separable scaling

4. Validation

Validation dataset

50 operating points, 10 repeated measurements per point
 z_m in [3.5, 23.5] mm, f_m in [1, 10] Hz

Fig. 7: Comparison between experimental data and model predictions for swarm radii, a) for r_1 , b) for r_2

0.25 mm RMSE for r_1	0.42 mm RMSE for r_2	6.49% MAE for r_1
9.12% MAE for r_2	0.16 Sx/Sy stiffness anisotropy	< 1 mm control-oriented prediction

Reference tracking

Fig. 8: Simulated MIMO PID tracking compared with open-loop experimental measurements, a) for r_1 , b) for r_2

Conclusion

The reduced-order ellipse model predicts stable ellipsoidal swarm morphology with sub-millimeter error, captures effective stiffness anisotropy, and provides a compact basis for control-oriented morphology regulation.